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First record of *Aenigmatias spatulatus* (Diptera: Phoridae) and its taxonomic significance for the Egyptian fauna

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Abstract

This study documents the first occurrence of *Aenigmatias spatulatus* (Liu and Wang, 2011) (Diptera: Phoridae) in Egypt. The research was conducted in Ismailia from October 2023 to December 2024 during mulberry silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. (Lepidoptera and Bombycidae) rearing trials. Several silkworm larvae were found dead and subsequently colonized by dipterous larvae, which were reared to adulthood for taxonomic identification. The adults were confirmed as *A. spatulatus*, a species originally described in China in 2011. This record not only represents the first detection of the species in Egypt but also the first documentation of its higher taxonomic groups in the country, including the subfamily Aenigmatiinae, tribe Aenigmatiini, and genus *Aenigmatias* Meinert, 1890. The discovery extends the known geographic range of the genus from Asia to North Africa, providing new insights into the diversity of Phoridae in the Middle East. These findings emphasize the importance of systematic monitoring of insect biodiversity associated with sericulture and contribute to a broader understanding of phorid fly distributions.

Introduction

The genus *Aenigmatias* (Meinert, 1890) is distinguished by its pronounced sexual dimorphism, with females being apterous and larvae developing as parasitoids of ant pupae. One of its most remarkable behavioral traits is the ability of males to carry and disperse females. This phenomenon was first reported by Schmitz (1955), who observed that during copulation the female, hidden beneath the male's abdomen, is carried in flight by the male. Although direct field

observations remain scarce, indirect evidence strongly supports this behavior. For example, Malaise trap captures consistently reveal equal numbers of males and females (Goto and Takeno, 1983 and present study; B. Brown, pers. comm.).

Intraspecific phoresy has also been documented in other phorid species. For instance, males of *Puliciphora borinquensis* are capable of transporting apterous females for at least 3.6 m in a single flight (Miller, 1979), with the possibility of even

greater distances. Miller's experimental design limited the maximum distance recorded, but his findings demonstrated that males frequently engage in successive flights with different females, suggesting their role in relocating mates to suitable oviposition sites. Similarly, males of *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) may disperse fully winged females during copulation; however, since females retain functional wings, this case is considered a less definitive example of true intraspecific phoresy (Miller, 1979).

Few insect families exhibit such diversity of body forms and life histories as the Phoridae, commonly referred to as humpbacked or scuttle flies. In tropical forests, in particular, the potential for discovering novel and highly specialized species remains high. Phorid flies demonstrate extraordinary adaptations in feeding, mating, and dispersal behaviors. They are nearly ubiquitous across ecosystems worldwide and are represented by a seemingly vast number of species. Their morphological diversity and ecological versatility have allowed them to adapt to a wide array of food sources, making generalizations about their biology difficult. While some phorids are commonly identified as scavengers, this characterization is overly simplistic. The widespread perception of them as scavengers stems from the prevalence of a few such species, whereas many others occupy parasitic or specialized ecological niches.

Despite the increasing knowledge of phorid diversity worldwide, records of *Aenigmatias* species remain extremely scarce, and no representatives of the subfamily Aenigmatiinae have previously been reported from Egypt or the Middle East. In this study, we document for the first time the occurrence of *Aenigmatias spatulatus* (Liu and Wang, 2011) (Diptera:

Phoridae) during mulberry silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. (Lepidoptera and Bombycidae) rearing trials in Ismailia, Egypt. This finding represents not only the first record of the species in Egypt but also the first documentation in the country of its higher taxonomic groups, including the subfamily Aenigmatiinae, tribe Aenigmatiini, and genus *Aenigmatias*. The study contributes to a better understanding of phorid biodiversity and expands the known geographical range of this unique lineage from Asia into North Africa.

Materials and methods

1. Silkworm rearing:

Eggs of the mulberry silkworm *B. mori* were obtained from the Sericulture Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute. Larvae were reared in the Plant Protection Department laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt, from October 2023 to December 2024. Standard rearing practices were followed (Mahmoud, 2017), and fresh mulberry leaves were provided to larvae four times daily. At the end of the rearing season, dead and infected larvae were observed and isolated for further examination. Dipterous larvae and eggs were detected inside fungal mycelia and spores associated with the silkworm cadavers. All dead larvae were collected and transferred to plastic jars, sealed with muslin cloth and secured with rubber bands, until the emergence of adult flies for taxonomic identification.

2. External morphology:

A morphological study was conducted on the newly recorded phorid fly *A. spatulatus*, representing the subfamily Aenigmatiinae, tribe Aenigmatiini, and genus *Aenigmatias* Meinert, 1890, recorded for the first time in Egypt.

3. Specimen investigations:

Specimens were examined under a stereomicroscope (Optika, Italy) (Plate

4 and Figure 6). Dissection: Insect body parts were dissected with fine forceps, removed from specimens, spread as much as possible, and mounted on points. Selected structures (Mouthparts, antennae, legs, and halteres) were treated in 10% KOH solution, thoroughly rinsed with tap water, dehydrated in 70% ethanol, cleared in xylene, and mounted in Canada balsam (Károlyi *et al.*, 2014).

Genitalia preparation: The posterior abdominal segments were removed and macerated in cold KOH. Male and female genitalia were examined separately. Female genitalia were treated in 10% KOH for 24 hours, dehydrated, cleared, and mounted in Canada balsam. Drawings were prepared from pinned specimens and microscopic slides using a stereomicroscope (40× magnification). Genital structures were examined in glycerin under a light microscope (40× magnification) (Sukontason and Vogtsberger, 2004 and Wolf and Liu, 1996).

4. Taxonomic framework:

Taxonomic terminology in this study follows standard phorid references. Comparative examination of specimens was carried out with phorid samples preserved in Egyptian insect collections, including the Egyptian Reference Museum of Insects, Ministry of Agriculture, Dokki, Cairo. The Insect Museum, Survey and Classification Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Ministry of Agriculture. Identification keys, diagnostic characters of subfamilies, genera, and species were consulted for confirmation.

Results and discussion

1. Survey:

This study was conducted from October 2023 to December 2024 in Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. Insect samples were collected from multiple

regions across the governorate and examined in the laboratory. Among the collected material, representatives of the family Phoridae were identified. Remarkably, the survey revealed a new record for Egypt: the subfamily Aenigmatiinae Schmitz, 1929; the tribe Aenigmatiini; the genus *Aenigmatias* Meinert, 1890; and the species *A. spatulatus*. This finding represents the first confirmed occurrence of the genus *Aenigmatias* in Egypt, adding to the known diversity of Phoridae in the region.

2. Taxonomy:

The taxonomic results confirmed the presence of a newly recorded lineage within the Egyptian phorid fauna. The classification of the recorded species is as follows: Family: Phoridae Curtis, 1833, Subfamily: Aenigmatiinae Schmitz, 1929, Tribe: Aenigmatiini, Genus: *Aenigmatias* Meinert, 1890, Species: *A. spatulatus*. The family Phoridae, commonly known as scuttle flies, is globally distributed and comprises over 4,000 described species (Disney, 1983 and 1994). Members of this family are characterized by reduced wing venation and a distinctive humpbacked body form. Their larvae exhibit diverse ecological roles, including saprophagy, fungivory, predation, and parasitoidism, although they are not considered true parasites (Elsheakh *et al.*, 2024). The discovery of *A. spatulatus* in Egypt expands the known distribution of the subfamily Aenigmatiinae beyond its previously reported range in Asia (Liu *et al.*, 2011) and highlights the need for further surveys to uncover additional phorid diversity in the region.

Family: Phoridae

Family Phoridae Curtis 1833.

Phoridae Curtis 1833, Brit, Ent, Pl,437.

Phorites Newman, 1834, Ent,

Mag.2:396.

Phoridae Haliday, 1851, in Walkers Ins, Brit, Dipt, 1:9.

For other synonyms refer to Handlirsch, in Schroder (1925 :1000 10010).
 See Collin, 1949a: Hafez, 1947: Schmitz, 1929, 1938, 1939, 1949: Seguy, 1938, 1940, Many more
 Phoridae should be eventually found.
Aphiochaeta aritalis Malloch.
 Bull. Brook. Ent. Soc., vol. IX. No. 3, June, 1914, P. 57.
 Type male: Havana, Illinois, September 20, 1895(A. Hempel). Acc. No. 13709.
Aphiochaeta bisetulata Malloch.
 Bull. Brook. Ent. Soc., vol. x, No. 3 July, 1915, p, 65.
 Type female: Urbana, Illinois, June 14, 1914 (E. H. Swigert).
Aphiochaeta nasoni Malloch.
 Bull. Brook. Ent. Soc., vol. IX, No. 3 June, 1914, P.58.
 Type male: Algonquin, Illinois, November 16, 1896 (W. A. Nason).
Aphiochaeta pallidiventris Malloch.
 Bull. Brook. Soc., vol., XI, v, No. 2 April, 1919, p.47.
 Type female: cobden, Illinois, May 9, 1918 (J.R.Maloch).
Aphiochaeta plebela Malloch.
 Bull. Brook, Ent, Soc., vol. IX, No. 3 June 1914, p.59.
 Type male: urbana, Illionols, reared from decaying vegetation, July 18, 1885. Acc. No. 6889.
 Lectoallotype female: urbana Illinois, reared from decaying vegetation, July 18, 1885. Acc, No. 6889.
 Paratype female: Urbana, Illinois, reared from decaying vegetation, July 18, 1885. Acc. No. 6889.

Synonyms

Tarsophoromyia Beyer, 1965,
 Metaplastophora Beyer, 1965
 Hemiplastophora Beyer, 1965,
 Obelosia Lioy, 1864 Trisometopia Lioy, 1864, Aphiochaeta Brues, 1904
 Trichometopia Bezzi and Stein, 1907
 Byrsophrys Enderlein, 1912
 Mallochina Schmitz, 1938,
 Heterophora Borgmeier, 1923 Lioyella

Enderlein, 1924
 Parametopina Borgmeier, 1924
 Pogonopleura Enderlein, 1924
 Stirocnemia Enderlein, 1927
 Epimegaselia Beyer, 1959
 Quasipseudacteon Beyer, 1959.

Descriptions of Family: Phoridae:

The Phoridae family, commonly referred to as scuttle flies, comprises approximately 4,000 described species and is regarded as one of the largest families within the order Diptera. Members of this family are globally distributed and are readily distinguished by their reduced wing venation and characteristic humpbacked body shape. The larvae exhibit diverse ecological roles, ranging from parasitoids and specialized predators to herbivores, fungivores, and polyphagous saprophages; however, they are not considered true parasites (Elsheakh *et al.*, 2024). Despite this diversity, the biology of most species remains poorly understood and requires further investigation (Disney, 1983 and 1994).

A new record of Subfamily, Trib, Genus, and Species:

In this study, a new record of the subfamily, tribe, genus, and species is reported: Aenigmatiinae Schmitz, 1929; Aenigmatiini; *Aenigmatias* Meinert, 1890; *A. spatulatus*

Subfamily: Aenigmatiinae

A recent revision of the New World Aenigmatiinae has demonstrated that among the five Neotropical genera previously included in this subfamily, only Cyrtophorina may form a monophyletic lineage with the type of genus *Aenigmatias*. Here, we present the first descriptions of male specimens from the genera *Borgmeieriphora*, *Colyeria*, and *Melittophora*. Based on male morphological characteristics, these genera, collectively referred to as the *Melittophora* group, are reassigned to the subfamily Metopininae and are closely related to the *Apocephalus* genus group. Three new species of

Borgmeieriphora are described: *B. multisetosa* (Costa Rica), *B. greigae* (Costa Rica), and *B. leptotarsa* (Panama). Observations of two species indicate that adult *Borgmeieriphora* are associated with army ants of the genus *Eciton*, where they may act as parasitoids. A new genus, *Cootiphora* gen. nov., represented by the type species *C. angustata* sp. nov. from Ecuador, is described and placed within the *Melittophora* group. A phylogenetic analysis of the *Melittophora* group suggests that *Colyeria* is the sister taxon to *Borgmeieriphora*, although the relationships among *Melittophora*, *Cootiphora*, *Colyeria*, and *Borgmeieriphora* remain unresolved. Within *Borgmeieriphora*, *B. multisetosa* and *B. greigae* are identified as sister taxa, while *B. kempfi* forms a sister relationship to this pair. *B. leptotarsa* is positioned as the sister taxon to all other species in the genus. The phylogenetic placement of Platydiptheron, another potential member of the *Melittophora* group, is currently unclear. Ongoing examinations of male specimens from Aenigmatiinae across other geographic regions aim to further clarify these relationships.

Recent analyses have demonstrated that certain genera may belong to a monophyletic group that also includes *Aenigmatias*. The convergence between the true aenigmatiine genera and those of the *Melittophora* group is reflected in their shared limuloid body shape, a trait interpreted as a defensive adaptation associated with life in the nests of social insects. Species of the scuttle fly subfamily Aenigmatiinae are well known for their pronounced sexual dimorphism, with females being apterous, halterless, and exhibiting a limuloid or cockroach-like morphology (Peterson, 1987). This morphology has been associated with the ecological observation that nearly all

Aenigmatiinae are myrmecophilic and, less frequently, termitophilic. For instance, *Aenigmatias lubbockii* (Verrall) (Diptera: Phoridae) parasitizes the pupae of *Formica fusca* (Linnaeus) and *F. picea* (Nylander). Other species, such as *A. dorni*, have been recorded in nests of *F. rufibarbis* and *F. glebaria*, while *A. franzi* has been captured in proximity to colonies of *Lasius niger* and *Myrmica ruginodis* (Schmitz, 1955; Smith, 1977 and Disney, 1994 and 2002).

The genus *Aenigmatias* was first erected by Meinert (1890) to accommodate his newly described species *A. blattoides*, *A. lubbockii* (Verrall), based on a female specimen collected from a nest of *F. fusca*. Meinert noted that the female more closely resembled a juvenile of the cockroach *Ectobius lapponicus* (Linnaeus) than a dipteran fly. The genus is typified by *Aenigmatias blattoides* Meinert, 1890, and is distinguished by its sexual dimorphism: females are wingless, while the larvae develop as parasites on ant cocoons.

Globally, the genus *Aenigmatias* (Subfamily: Aenigmatiinae) includes a diverse assemblage of species. Six species are known from Europe (Schmitz, 1955 and 1956) and seven from North America (Borgmeier, 1963). Additional species have been described from Asia, including *A. dorni* (Enderlein) from Japan (Goto and Takeno, 1983) and *A. gotoi* Disney (2002). More recently, *A. spatulatus*, was recorded from China. Overall, the recognition of these subfamilies and genera highlights the complex diversity and evolutionary adaptations within the Phoridae. The findings of this study emphasize that while phorid flies are frequently associated with parasitic interactions, they do not represent true parasites. Instead, their behavior is largely driven by their attraction to

mucus-like substances and ant-associated microhabitats.

Descriptions of Subfamily:

Aenigmatiinae:

A revision of the Aenigmatiinae of the New World has shown that only one of the five neotropical genera currently included in this subfamily, the genus *Cyrtophorina*, may belong to a monophyletic group that includes the type of genus *Aenigmatias*. Here we present the description of the first male specimens ever encountered in the genera *Borgmeieriphora*, *Colyeria*, and *Melittophora*. Based on the structure of the males, these three genera, referred to here as the *Melittophora* group, belong to the subfamily Metopininae and are related to the genus group *Apocephalus*. Three new species of *Borgmeieriphora* are described: *B. multisetosa* from Costa Rica, *B. greigae* from Costa Rica, and *B. leptotarsa* from Panama. Observation of two species has revealed that adult *Borgmeieriphora* are associated with legionary ants of the genus *Eciton*, of which they may be parasitoids. *Cootiphora* gen nov., represented by the type species *C. angustata* sp nov., from Ecuador, is described here and placed in the *Melittophora* group. A phylogeny of the genera of the *Melittophora* group shows their possible relationships: *Colyeria* is the sister taxon of *Borgmeieriphora*, while the relationships among *Melittophora*, *Cootiphora*, *Colyeria*, and *Borgmeieriphora* cannot be clarified. In *Borgmeieriphora*, the species *B. multisetosa* and *B. greigae* are sister taxa, while *B. kempfi* is the sister taxon to *B. multisetosa* and *B. greigae*, and *B. leptotarsa* is the sister taxon to all other species. The relationships within the genus *Platydipteron*, another possible member of the *Melittophora* group, are unknown. Examination of males from representative genera of Aenigmatiinae from other geographic regions has

demonstrated that they may belong to a monophyletic group that also includes *Aenigmatias*. The convergence between true aenigmatiine genera and. The genera of the *Melittophora* group are manifested in the limuloid shape of the body, a characteristic that may be a defensive adaptation related to life in the nests of social insects. Species of the scuttle fly subfamily Aenigmatiinae have long been known for their marked sexual dimorphism, with females being apterous, haltere less, and limuloid or cockroach-like in appearance (Peterson, 1987). The female morphology has been linked to the fact that almost all Aenigmatiinae have been recorded as being either myrmecophilic or, more rarely, termitophilic. *Aenigmatias lubbockii* (Verrall) (Diptera: Phoridae) is known to parasitize the pupae of the ants *Formica fusca* (Linnaeus) and *F. picea* (Nylander), whereas other species such as *A. dorni*, have been observed in nests of *F. rufibarbis* and *F. glebaria*, and *A. franzi* was caught in the vicinity of *Lasius niger* and *Myrmica ruginodis* (Schmitz, 1955; Smith, 1977; Disney, 1994 and 2002 and Disney and Sinclair, 1979). The genus *Aenigmatias* was erected by Meinert (1890) to accommodate his new species *A. blattoides* *A. lubbockii* (Verrall), which was described from a female specimen collected from a *F. fusca* nest. He described the female as looking more like a juvenile of the cockroach *Ectobius lapponicus* (Linnaeus) than as an actual fly (Meinert, 1890).

Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

The Genus: Type Species: *Aenigmatias blattoides* Meinert, 1890 *Aenigmatias* was erected by Meinert (1890) to accommodate his new species, *A. blattoides* and *A. lubbockii* (Verrall), which were described from a female specimen collected from a *F. fusca* nest.

The genus *Aenigmatias* Meinert is revised with the description of three new species: *A. longicornis* sp. nov., *A. primitivus* sp. nov., and *A. nigeroticus* sp. nov., all of which are recognized and illustrated. *Protoplatyphora* Brues is synonymized with *Aenigmatias*, and its single previously described species is here transferred as *A. tertiaris* (Brues), comb. nov. Similarly, *Chaetopleurophora bisetosa* Brown, 2007 is reassigned to *Aenigmatias* as *A. bisetosus*, comb. nov. In addition, an unrelated fossil resembling *Aenigmatias* is described as *Pseudaenigmatias ctenitibia* gen. et sp. nov., which is placed within a modern termitophilous clade. *Limulomyia tyche* Brown, 1999, is interpreted as representing a distinct, highly limuloid lineage, unrelated to either of the other two limuloid groups. A diagnostic key to fossil *Aenigmatias* is provided, alongside a phylogenetic analysis of fossil taxa. These fossil records offer significant insights into the evolutionary development of the limuloid body form characteristic of modern *Aenigmatias* species.

Genus: Synonyms

<i>Aenigmatias</i> Meinert,	1890
<i>Platyphora</i> Verrall, 1877	
<i>Aegnimatias</i> Meinert,	1890
<i>Psalidesma</i> Becker, 1912	
<i>Oniscomyia</i> Enderlein,	1908
<i>Pseudaenigmatias</i> Brown, 2016.	
<i>Platyphorella</i> Strand, 1917.	

These synonymies reflect the extensive taxonomic revisions within the subfamily Aenigmatiinae and the challenges posed by the extreme morphological dimorphism of females.

Descriptions of Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

Diagnostic Characters of *Aenigmatias*

Members of the genus *Aenigmatias* can be readily distinguished from other phorid genera by the following diagnostic traits:

Head: Frons broader than high, usually brown, with sparse short hair. Eyes

bare; ocellar triangle with short setae. Palpus brown, bearing 4–6 short bristles. Antennae with enlarged first segment; flagellomere globose; arista subapical.

Thorax: Broader than the head, scutum dark brown to blackish, with one short dorsal bristle on each side. Scutellum extending posteriorly, partially covering the first abdominal tergite. Wings (males only): Hyaline or faintly tinged; veins brown, with Rs bearing numerous short hairs. Vein M1 curved anteriorly, not sharply deflected apically. CuA₁ bisinuate, extending to the wing margin. Legs: Femora yellow to brown; fore tibia stout with dorsal palisade. Fore tarsus flattened and dilated, tapering distally. Mid and hind tibiae with distinct rows of palisade setae.

Abdomen: Dark brown, broader than long; tergites with concave posterior margins. Males: terminalia asymmetrical, epandrium with characteristic paired processes. Females: apterous, halterless, with limuloid (“cockroach-like”) body shape. These characters, particularly the wing reduction and limuloid body morphology in females, together with the highly dimorphic male-female body plan, provide the key traits separating *Aenigmatias* from related phorid genera.

Biological notes of *Aenigmatias*:

Species of *Aenigmatias* exhibit highly specialized biological and ecological traits, reflecting their close evolutionary associations with social insects: Myrmecophily and Parasitism. Most species are myrmecophilic, developing within ant nests, where their larvae parasitize ant pupae. Less frequently, some records suggest associations with termites. Sexual Dimorphism: A hallmark of the genus is extreme dimorphism: Males are fully winged and capable of dispersal. Females are apterous, halterless, and exhibit a

limuloid (Cockroach-like) morphology, an adaptation for living within host nests. Phoresy (Male-Assisted Dispersal): Males play a key role in dispersal by carrying wingless females during copulation. This behavior, termed intraspecific phoresy, has been observed directly in some species and inferred in others through equal male-to-female ratios in Malaise trap captures.

Ecological role:

The genus is an important component of ant-associated communities. While often described as parasites, their biology is more nuanced, with adult flies being strongly attracted to ant-associated substrates and microhabitats rather than being obligate parasites.

Distribution:

Aenigmatias has been reported from Europe, North America, and Asia. The present study documents the first record of *A. spatulatus* in Egypt, expanding the known range of the genus into North Africa. Species of *Aenigmatias* exhibit adaptations that appear linked to intraspecific phoretic behavior, including male-assisted airlifting and dispersal of females.

Diagnostic morphological features include:

Head: Frons brown, broader than high, with sparse short hairs; eyes bare; ocellar triangle bearing two short bristles; palpus brown with 4–6 short bristles.

Thorax: Broader than the head; scutum blackish-brown, bearing one short dorsal bristle on each side. Wings: Hyaline. eggs: Femora yellow to brownish-yellow; fore tibia stout with a dorsal palisade; fore tarsus dilated and flattened, gradually narrowing distally.

Abdomen: Terga blackish-brown; terga 3–5 with posterior margins concave; tergum 6 with an anteriorly concave margin; venter greyish-pale.

Biological notes: Members of the subfamily Aenigmatiinae are notable for their extreme sexual dimorphism, with females consistently described as apterous, haltereless, and possessing a limuloid or cockroach-like body form (Peterson, 1987). These morphological traits are strongly associated with their myrmecophilic lifestyle and are likely adaptations for survival within the nests of social insects.

Background female: Morphology in the subfamily Aenigmatiinae has been consistently associated with myrmecophily and, less frequently, termitophily (Peterson, 1987). For example, *Aenigmatias lubbockii* (Verrall) (Diptera: Phoridae) is known to parasitize the pupae of the ants *Formica fusca* (Linnaeus) and *F. picea* (Nylander). Other species display similar ecological relationships: *A. dorni* has been collected from nests of *F. rufibarbis* and *F. glebaria*, while *A. franzi* has been captured in association with *Lasius niger* and *Myrmica ruginodis* (Schmitz, 1955; Smith, 1977; Disney, 1994 and 2002; and Disney and Sinclair, 1979).

Taxonomic notes:

The genus *Aenigmatias* was established by Meinert (1890) to accommodate his new species *A. blattoides* and *A. lubbockii* (Verrall), based on a female specimen collected from a *Formica fusca* nest. Meinert noted that the female bore a striking resemblance to the juvenile stage of the cockroach *Ectobius lapponicus* (Linnaeus), rather than to a dipteran fly. This observation highlighted the extreme morphological divergence within the genus, particularly in the flightless females.

Species Description:

Aenigmatias spatulatus Liu and Wang, 2011

Male (Plate 1, Figures 1–4; Plate 2, Figures 1–2):

Body length: 2.25–2.50 mm.

Head: Frons brown, broader than high, sparsely covered with short hair. Eyes bare. Ocellar triangle with two short bristles; each side of the anterior ocellus with a single bristle. First antennal segment enlarged; flagellomere 1 brown and globose; arista subapical. Palpus brown with 4–6 short apical bristles. Proboscis small.

Thorax: Broader than head; scutum blackish-brown with a short dorsal bristle on each side. The scutellum extended posteriorly, covering the first abdominal tergite.

Wings: Hyaline, faintly tinged with brownish-grey; all veins brown except A1+CuA2, which is yellowish-brown. Vein M1 curved anteriorly, not deflected apically; vein CuA1 bisinuate, extending to wing margin; vein A1+CuA2 weak and nearly straight, disappearing at approximately the distal one-sixth of the wing. Rs with 19–22 short hairs; axillary margin with 10 hairs. Halteres brown.

Legs: Predominantly brown, with coxae and most femora yellow to brownish-yellow. Fore tibia stout, with a dorsal palisade. Fore tarsus dilated and flattened, gradually tapering distally; first tarsomere as wide as the apex of the fore tibia. The mid tibia bears anterodorsal, dorsal, and posterodorsal palisades, with the dorsal row disappearing in the distal one-third. Hind tibia with three palisades, the dorsal row extending nearly the full length.

Abdomen: Terga blackish-brown, broader than long, clothed with minute hairs. Tergum 1 shortened medially; terga 3–5 with posterior margins concave; tergum 6 with a distinctly concave anterior margin. Abdomen and Terminalia: Venter greyish-pale. Male terminalia are mostly retracted beneath tergum 6, shining, yellowish to brown, small, and asymmetrical. The epandrium is large, bearing two pairs of processes in addition to a hook-like

process at the right posteroventral corner. The posterior right half of the epandrium is weakly membranous. The left upper process is finger-shaped with short hairs; the left lower process is robust, longer and wider than the upper, rounded apically and bearing short hairs. The right upper process is thick, oriented inward, and pointed distally, with short hairs; the right lower process is elongated and spoon-shaped. Hypandrium bilobed, proximally fused, clothed with short hairs.

Female (Plate 3, Figures (1 and 5); Plate 4, Figures 1–4)

Body length: 1.3 mm. Apterous, with halteres absent.

Thorax and Abdomen: The division between the thorax and abdomen is distinct. Thorax reduced; pronotum very small, mesonotum humped, metanotum forming a saddle-shaped depression with the anterior part of the first abdominal segment. The Thoracic notum is undivided; together with the first three abdominal segments, laterally expanded to exceed head width. Segmental length (measured along lateral margin): thorax + first three abdominal segments total ~825 µm. Lateral and ventrolateral extensions of these segments are covered with acantha or microtrichia. Mean spacing between microtrichia measured at the midline of notal extensions. The posterior half of the metanotum and metapleuron lacks setae and microtrichia, appearing smooth.

Spiracles: The first thoracic spiracle is positioned dorsolateral on the notum.

Legs: Fore tarsus approximately one-third the length of tibia; mid-tarsus, tarsomere 1 about half tibial length; hind tarsus, tarsomere 1 half tibial length. Protarsomere 1 is about one-third the combined length of protarsomeres 2–5. All tarsomeres are cylindrical, bearing mostly unspecialized setae and microtrichia, with several fine acute-tipped (FAT)

setae along the ventral midline. No ventral flattened setae on fore and mid legs. Hind tarsomere 1 with two rows of palisade-like flattened setae, resembling those of the male. Claws and pulvilli unmodified; pulvilli medium-sized, pad-shaped.

General Features: The first three abdominal segments covered with microtrichia; claws and pulvilli as in the male. Mid and hind tarsi unmodified.

Specimens examined: Ismailia, (8-2024, 9-2024), (Total: 8, Male 6, Female 2). This species is documented herein for the first time in Egypt by Elsheakh. The identification and voucher specimens have been deposited in the Egyptian Reference Insect Museum (ERIM), Department of Insect Taxonomy and Survey, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center. All specimens are preserved under the curatorial responsibility of the author. This species is documented herein for the first time in Egypt by Elsheakh. The identification and voucher specimens have been deposited in the Egyptian Reference Insect Museum (ERIM), Department of Insect Taxonomy and Survey, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center. All specimens are preserved under the curatorial responsibility of the author. Specimens Examined Location: Ismailia, Egypt Collection dates:

August–September 2024, Specimens: 8 males, 6 females, 2 additional females, Repository: Egyptian Reference Insect Museum (ERIM), Department of Insect Taxonomy and Survey, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt Curatorial responsibility: Elsheakh.

This study reports the first record of *A. spatulatus* in Egypt, marking the first documentation of the subfamily Aenigmatiinae, tribe Aenigmatiini, and genus *Aenigmatias* in the country. The species exhibits extreme sexual dimorphism: winged males capable of dispersal and apterous, limuloid females adapted for life within ant nests. Observations underscore the ecological specialization of *A. spatulatus*, including myrmecophily and male-assisted female dispersal (Intraspecific phoresy). These findings emphasize the importance of monitoring insect communities associated with sericulture, as such studies can uncover previously unrecorded species and provide insights into evolutionary adaptations and ecological interactions.

Future research should focus on the ecological role, distribution, and potential impacts of *A. spatulatus* on both ant communities and silkworm rearing systems in Egypt.

Plate (1)

Sub family: Aenigmatiinae:

Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(1) Thorax of Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(2) Abdomen of Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(3) femora of Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(4)

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(1) Thorax of male (2) Abdomen of male (3) Leg of male (4) Head of Phoridae spp.

a pprn s, anterior postpronotal seta: b pprn s, basal postpronotal seta: npl s, notopleuron:npl s, notopleural seta: sbap sctcl s, subapical scutellar seta bsctcl, subscutellum sbvb s, subvibrissal seta sct, scutum sctcl, scutellum setscctcl sut, scutoscuteellar suture spal area, supra-alar area spal s, supra-alar seta spvb s, supravibrissal seta: pal s, postalar seta.

Plate (2)

Sub family: Aenigmatiinae:

Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(1) left lateral view of thorax of *Aenigmatias* spp. (2) Right wing dorsal views of *Aenigmatias* spp.

Abbreviations: anepm, anepimeron; anepst, anepisternum; a spr, anterior spiracle; cx, coxa ;hit, halter; kepm,katepimeron; kepst, katepisternum; ktg, katatergite; mtn, metanotum; plrtrch, pleurotrochantin; sct, scutum; sct., scutellum; trn sut, transverse suture; C, costal vein; CuA, basal part of anterior branch of cubital vein CuA1, CuA , branches of anterior branch of cubital vein M, medial vein, R, radius R1, anterior branch of radius; Rs, radial sector, branching again into R R R' Sc, subcostal.

Plate (3)

Sub family: Aenigmatiinae:

Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(1), (2): Leg of female Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011. (3) (A) Dorsal(above, right) and ventral (below, left) views of eggs. (B) Lateral view of eggs, (4) Larve of *Aenigmatias spatulatus*, (5) Larve of *Aenigmatias spatulatus*, (6) A stereo microscope, binuclear Optika Italy (1) pupa of *Megaselia*.

Plate (4)

Sub family: Aenigmatiinae:

Genus: *Aenigmatias*;

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

Figure: Fore-leg of *Aenigmatias spatulatus* (Liu and Wang) female (A) and fore-leg tarsus (B)

Species: *Aenigmatias spatulatus* Liu and Wang, 2011

(1) Adult Female (2) Abdomen (3) Leg.

(4) A: Egg B: Pupa C, D: Larve of Phoridae.

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